

SPIRITUAL AND MORAL EDUCATION OF STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract : The article talks about the main methods and methods of teaching a foreign language that contribute to the spiritual and moral education of students. The characteristics of these methods in the educational process are presented. Focuses on the special role of English as a tool of international communication, through which students get acquainted with examples of world and national culture.

Key words: spiritual and moral education, foreign language, teaching methods and methods, national culture.

Today, in the conditions of rapid development of society, spiritual and moral education of the young generation is considered the most important aspect of personal development. Education plays an important role in raising a well-rounded person. It is necessary for teachers to build confidence in students for the future, love for motherland, culture, language , kindness, conscientiousness, courage and tolerance, sense of justice, desire for knowledge and enlightenment. All this forms the awareness of the national identity, love and respect for one's nation, and is confused about its development and growth . Therefore, we can see in the works and reports of the heads of state that serious attention is paid to this issue in Uzbekistan. For example, the thoughts of the First President I.A. Karimov that "Spirituality is an incomparable force that calls a person to spiritual purification, to the heart , strengthens the inner world of a person, strengthens his will, completes his faith, awakens his conscience" It is a sign of large-scale work on education. Today, the head of our state also mentions this issue in his lectures. President of Uzbekistan

Shavkat Mirziyoyev said at the meeting: "If the body of society's life is the economy, then its soul and spirit is spirituality, - Since we decided to build a new Uzbekistan, we rely on two strong pillars. The first is a strong economy based on market principles . The second is a strong spirituality based on the rich heritage of our ancestors and national values" [2]. In fact, the positive formation of a person's culture, spirituality, education and culture is a sign of the correct and fair policy being conducted in the country.

A person and the whole nation entering the universal cultural space should own various means of inter-ethnic communication. From this point of view, knowledge of at least one foreign language plays a huge role. The process of teaching foreign languages to modern students includes a unique pedagogical potential for moral , aesthetic and labor education of the young generation. It introduces students to the world and motherhood models cultures, brings them into the dialogue of cultures. Teaching foreign languages has a clearly defined cultural orientation. Patriotism and the culture of inter-ethnic relations are closely related . World scientists M.Borishevskiy, "An important feature of human spirituality is its universal character, which is manifested in any manifestation of activity: everything a person has, how he behaves, what values and needs motivate his activity" reflected in his works. We know very well that the theoretical justification of the pedagogical conditions for the spiritual and moral education of students in English language classes consists in the analysis of the main methods used by teachers in teaching.

A foreign language is open to the use of the content of various fields of knowledge, as well as the content of other academic subjects. When studying foreign languages, students need to learn and master the following:

1. world culture, the national cultures of the peoples of the countries where the language is being studied are reflected in their way of life and style of people;
2. spiritual heritage of countries and peoples, their historical and cultural memory;
3. Ways to achieve intercultural understanding.

Among the topics discussed in the process of learning foreign languages, there are many actual problems. Among them, problems of tolerance, problems of modern family, problems of charity, problems of environmental protection, fight against drugs, problems of material and national culture, problems of poverty and others are distinguished.

In the foreign language class, students get acquainted with the history and traditions of the countries where the language is being studied, and learn other cultures. And by getting to know other people's lives, they can design their own lives. An important aspect of such lessons is to increase the amount of knowledge about the specific features of the culture of one's native country, as well as the history of one's city and region.

In the modern teaching of a foreign language in every educational institution, various methods are widely used that help the teacher to focus students' attention on the spiritual and moral values of humanity. These methods include :

team (group) work and pair work;

role play;

thematic training;

Working in pairs or small groups is one of the main ways to educate students in a foreign language class, because during such work, students discuss current issues, communicate with their peers, and express their opinions. At the end of such work, group members choose the most effective solution to the problem, justify their choice and provide strong arguments. In order to achieve the greatest speech activity of students, it is necessary to frequently use group work forms recognized domestically and abroad as one of the ways to increase the efficiency of modern foreign language lessons.

Pair work should be introduced from the first year of teaching English. So, for example, in the textbook "Total English" (Mark Foley, Dianne Hall) pair work is already presented from the "Starter" level.

Role playing game.

Another effective method is a role-playing game, usually conducted between several teams. It allows you to: form and develop professional competence, independently solve problems and apply acquired knowledge, as well as adapt to new situations and work in a team, and ultimately contribute to the socialization of students. The use of business games in foreign language classes helps to reveal the creative potential of each student, ideas, information and experience are exchanged during the game.

Unlike team work in a role-playing game, each student takes individual responsibility for the decision made, independently analyzes the effectiveness and expediency of a particular model of actions . To a large extent , the behavior of role-playing is determined by the language material being studied, but the moral orientation also affects the intended behavior.

Thematic lessons. Thematic lessons play an important role in the implementation of spiritual and moral education in the English language class. In such educational activities, students get to know the mentality and culture of the people who speak their native language. For example, conducting a thematic lesson "Countries Speaking English in Easter" allows students not only to get acquainted with the culture of other countries, but also to study the culture of their own country more deeply. As a result of the comparison of holidays in Great Britain and Ukraine, students identify common features and specific features, which helps to develop an understanding of foreign traditions and a good attitude towards the country as a whole .

In conclusion, it should be said that the following conclusions can be drawn based on the theoretical analysis and study of the advanced pedagogical experience on the problems of spiritual and moral education of students through learning a foreign language. Learning a foreign language improves moral and moral culture, develops logical thinking, has a great impact on memory, broadens one's worldview and increases general culture. In the process of language acquisition, professional theoretical knowledge, as well as educational-organizational, educational and

intellectual, educational and informational, educational and communicative skills are improved. Learning a foreign language contributes to moral and aesthetic development, affects the spiritual development of a person. In modern society, knowledge of a foreign language increases the rating of a specialist in any field, makes him competitive, and creates conditions for the comfortable performance of professional tasks.

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